

serial Number	Name	Age	Gender	Location	Occupation	The watercolor workshops have positively impacted my overall well-being.	Participating in the workshops has helped me manage stress and anxiety or any other issue.	Participating in the workshops has helped me manage stress and anxiety or any other issue.(OPTIONAL) Share only if your comfortable to share.
1	Pari Takle	37	Female	Thane	Housewife	Agree	Neutral	Nothing to share
2	Ridhima Gupta	35	Female	Meerut	Teacher	Agree	Agree	I love colors so yes it was an art therapy for me
3	Maruf Hyder Jafri	43	Male	Sidhpur	Proprietor- Art Gallery	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	No such stress... but it was fun . Enjoyed workshops
4	Bindu Gopinath	52	Female	Bangalore	Homemaker	Agree	Agree	I enjoyed the workshop very much . It gave me a new insight into painting.
5	Selvakumari	54	Female	Bangalore	Art teacher	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Yes.
6	Sae Vanjape	42	Female	Pune	Homemaker	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Yes painting is meditation for me.
7	Chitra	39	Female	Chennai	IT	Strongly agree	Agree	Yes helped to a great extent
8	Varsha	32	Female	Bangalore	Teacher	Agree	Neutral	Not really ...
9	Sugandha	42	Female	UAE	Housewife	Agree	Agree	Yes
10	Sindhu Dsouza	52	Female	Vashi, Navi Mumbai	Self Employed	Agree	Agree	Painting always keeps me happy and contended. I love to paint. It keeps me calm....patient
11	pinali	49	Female	nj	dental surgeon	Strongly agree	Neutral	Its my stress buster or zen for the day!
12	Madhura Butala	39	Female	Chinchwad	Architect	Neutral	Strongly agree	Yes
13	S Ram	50	Female	Thane	Teacher	Agree	Agree	Drawing and Painting are like meditation for me. So if meditation relieves stress, so does drawing.
14	Dr Vani Ravikumar	57 yrs	Female	Bangalore	Doctor- Pathologist	Strongly agree	Agree	The Landscape painting wokshop, helped me to paint better and improved my confidence. Thus made me happy and feel good.
15	Kiran Joshi	60 years	Female	Rajasthan	Retired	Agree	Agree	I loved doing it

16	Gurpreet	44	Female	Gurgaon	Artist	Neutral	Neutral	I joined it to improve my skill not not any anxiety or stress 😊
17	Susan	36	Female	Bangalore	Nursing officer	Neutral	Neutral	Ns
18	Dipika Jain	39	Female	Mysore	Homemaker	Strongly agree	Agree	No
19	Sonal	60yrs	Female	Vadodara	Free lancer	Agree	Agree	Improved artistic skills
20	Saloni Gupta	41	Female	Haryana	Teaching	Agree	Neutral	NA
21	Saranya senthil	38	Female	Tutucurin	Homemaker	Agree	Agree	Yes
22	Ashwini Jadhav	34	Female	Pune	Software engineer	Strongly agree	Agree	Didn't think over this
23	Anusha	28	Female	Kakinada	Housewife	Strongly agree	Agree	It helped me with stress
24	Neelam Sacheev	59	Female	Delhi	Homemaker	Agree	Agree	NA
25	Tanuj	37	Female	Maharashtra	Homemaker	Agree	Neutral	I wanted to learn new techniques
26	Jugnu	40	Female	Noida	Artist	Agree	Neutral	Not applicable
27	Mansi Nanavati	47	Female	Mumbai	Home maker	Agree	Neutral	Nothing to share
28	Pranav Pitre	42	Male	Belgaum	Professor	Agree	Neutral	Not particularly
29	CB.shanmugapriya	21	Female	Erode, Tamil Nadu	Process Executive, INFOSYS BPM	Agree	Agree	It helps to knowledge about basic water color theory
30	Veena Venugopal	39	Female	Bengaluru	Housewife	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Yes, it helps manage stress and anxiety. It helps center the wandering mind.
31	Deepak V	31	Male	Bengaluru	Lead Data Analyst	Agree	Neutral	NA
32	Shiraz Medhora	65	Female	Nagpur	Retired high school teacher	Agree	Agree	Realized my potential as an artist
33	Neha joshi	40	Female	Gujrat Kapadwanj	Self-employed	Agree	Strongly agree	Yes
34	Debarati	43	Female	Shimla	Analyst	Agree	Agree	NA
35	Sonal Verma	43	Female	Pune	IT industry	Agree	Neutral	-
36	Shailja Pandey	35	Female	Powai	Working	Strongly agree	Agree	Enhanced my creativity
37	Keerthana Krishnaraj	39	Female	Salem	Housewife	Agree	Neutral	Yes
38	Dr Sangita Limaye	53	Female	Thane	Ayurved consultant	Strongly agree	Agree	Happiness and mental satisfaction of completing dreams
39	Ranjana	60	Female	Himachal Pradesh	Retired	Agree	Neutral	It was enjoyable
40	Neera Chopra	54	Female	New Delhi	Central Government employee	Strongly agree	Agree	Yes I wish I could get more time
41	Tanushree Agarwal	40	Female	Varanasi	Business	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Has helped me realise my interest in art
42	V Vangala	49	Female	Hyderabad	IT	Agree	Neutral	Perhaps
43	Juthika Das	35	Female	Kolkata	Service	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	This workshops were well informative and stress bursting

44	Megha	35	Female	Pune	iT	Agree	Agree	Yes
45	Anagha Mota	40	Female	Mumbai	Paper artist ,scrapbooker, Vaastu consultant	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Due various allergys I had to leave art , but watercolour is one medium which has helped me again to follow my passion...it has helped reduce my stress level and practice mindfulness
46	Aboleee Zadbuke	26	Female	Pune	UI/UX designer	Agree	Agree	This workshop has encouraged me towards positive change
47	Kamna	38	Female	Bangalore	House wife	Agree	Agree	NA
48	Sampada Himanshu Gadgil	42 yrs.	Female	Mumbai	Homemaker	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Definitely all workshops are help me to manage my stress...
49	Sunita	35	Female	Hyderabad	IT	Agree	Agree	Yes it reduces stress when I paint
50	Vaneeta Rallan	59	Female	Gurugam	Art teacher	Agree	Agree	It has help me to improve
51	Amruta	30	Female	Mumbai	Homemaker	Agree	Agree	Yes
52	Khyati Thakkar	43	Female	Mumbai- suburban	Interior Designer	Agree	Agree	Not much. Practice and being in touch may help.
53	Vatsala Srivastava	39	Female	Tenga Valley, Arunachal Pradesh	House wife	Strongly agree	Agree	It has imparted a very positive impact on my wellbeing.
54	Laasya Anand	30	Female	Bangalore	Software Engineer	Agree	Agree	-
55	Sruthi Divvela	24	Female	Hyderabad	Data Engineer	Agree	Agree	NA
56	Dr Suprita Chandel	43	Female	Agra	Dental Surgeon	Agree	Agree	The outcome of the painting has given me lot of satisfaction and happiness
57	Asma	38	Female	Nagpur	Personality development coach	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree	Yes, workshop really have to manage stress and anxiety also to improve the concentration also boosted self esteem

									It has helped in dealing with daily anxiety and it brings a breath of fresh air in our daily routine of life and we can be more creative and mindful in our other activities also
58	Tehzib jafri	47	Female	Sidhpur	Housewife	Agree	Agree		
59	Gayatri	45	Female	Pune	IT	Strongly agree	Neutral		Na
60	Shallu Yadav	30	Female	Bikaner	Private	Agree	Agree		Stress
61	Aastha Garg	35	Female	Yamuna Nagar, Haryana	Artist	Agree	Strongly agree		Yes
62	Shifa Fathima	28	Female	Coimbatore	Art tutor	Strongly agree	Agree		Improved my perspective skill
63	Saipriya	30	Female	Hyderabad	Private employee	Agree	Agree		Na
64	Kanchan pawar	38	Female	Hubli	Art educator	Agree	Agree		Watercolours are therapeutic.
65	sujata ranka	63	Female	Nagpur	Housewife	Neutral	Neutral		Neutral
66	Amrita	35	Female	Bangalore	Software Professional	Agree	Agree		It gave me a medium to divert myself from the reality
67	Shreya Singh	40	Female	Mumbai	Art & Craft Teacher	Agree	Neutral		-
68	Jinal Chauhan	29	Female	Ahmedabad Gujarat	Student	Agree	Strongly agree		Decrease the anxiety and stress
69	Sujata Nagar	40	Female	PUNE	UX designer	Agree	Agree		Yes indeed it is very helpful to gain knowledge about watercolor medium.
70	Natesh	44	Male	Bangalore	IT engineer	Strongly agree	Neutral		Na
71	Aruna Parab	40	Female	Mumbai	IT	Strongly agree	Neutral		Not relevant
72	Mahitha	30	Female	California, USA	Software employee	Strongly agree	Strongly agree		Workshop is great. But I wish I practice often.
73	SONAL Mohile	40	Female	Virginia, USA	Teacher	Strongly agree	Agree		Yes, takes mind of anxious thoughts. Also gives hope to learn something
74	Mayuri	38	Female	Alibag	IT Professional	Strongly agree	Strongly agree		Painting has increased my 'Happy Hormones' and 'Feel Good Hormones' (Dopamine, Cortisol etc)
75	Jyoti	50	Female	USA	Software Engineer	Strongly agree	Neutral		Yes helped with procrastination to practice issue
76	Purnima Shabish	38	Female	New Delhi	Homemaker	Agree	Agree		-
77	Kanizfatema	41	Female	Nagpur	Housemaker	Strongly agree	Strongly agree		NA
78	Anjali Modi	45	Female	Flat no 402, vishwa rukhma apartment, wanjari nagar, nagpur	Home maker	Agree	Neutral		No
79	Archana Dharsini	28	Female	Ramathapuram , TamilNadu	Test Analyst	Neutral	Disagree		NA

80	Raksha Rajan Parab	21	Female	Bhandup Mumbai	Student	Agree	Agree	Developing skill
								It has helped me in taking out me time. In a joint family setup it was assumed that I will always be available for others.
81	Swati Raatogi	42	Female	Delhi	Homemaker	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	
82	Aparajita Mahato	39	Female	Bengaluru	Self-employed (teaching art to kids)	Strongly agree	Agree	To have more patience in life.
83	SARITHA N J	40	Female	Kerala	Banker	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Yes
								With my only daughter gone away for higher studies and husband too tied up in his job as a high ranking Police official, I was dealing with loneliness and isolation issues that were leading to borderline depression. These workshops helped me find a new direction, a new sense of identity for myself. Not to mention the creative satisfaction that provided a positive boost to my emotional well-being.
84	Anuradha Banerjee	49	Female	New Delhi	Homemaker	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	